

Fungal species, strains, and their ARSEF numbers.^a

Fungus species	Strain	ARSEF
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	BbE	714
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	Ma12	1432
<i>Hirsutella citriformis</i>	Hc490	490

^aUSDA-ARS Collection of Entomopathogenic Fungal Cultures, USDA-ARS Plant Protection Unit, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research at Cornell University, Tower Road, Ithaca, NY 14853-0331, USA; the isolates are also available from the Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute.

Conidia produced on the outside of the cadaver can infect healthy BPH. Insect fungus epizootics can completely control BPH populations.

Several chemical pesticides that suppress germination and growth of the insect fungi can prevent the occurrence of epizootics. We designed an experiment to illustrate these effects and to provide a simple test for studying the interaction between fungi and chemicals.

Three BPH pathogens—*Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill., *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch.) Sorokin, and *Hirsutella citriformis* Speare—were treated (see table) with technical formulations of the fungicides benomyl and edifenphos and the insecticide carbaryl.

Germination rates were determined by incubating 10⁶ conidia/ml of a 1% dextrose/0.5% yeast extract broth on a shaker machine. Pesticides were applied at 0.1, 1, 10, 100, and 1,000 ppm in 5 replications. After 24 h, at least 250 conidia of each replication were examined under the microscope for the presence of germination tubes. Germination rates were computed as

$$\text{germination (\%)} = 100\% \times \frac{\text{no. germinated conidia}}{\text{no. germinated conidia} + \text{no. not germinated conidia}}$$

Mycelium growth rates were determined in a 3% dextrose/1.5% yeast extract broth in shaker flasks. The flasks were inoculated with 1 ml conidia suspension (5 × 10⁶ conidia/ml). Mycelium dry weight was determined after 3 d of growth.

All concentrations of the pesticides tested inhibited conidia germination (see figure). *H. citriformis* was significantly

Effects of the pesticides benomyl, carbaryl, and edifenphos on the germination and mycelium growth of the insect fungi *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae*, and *H. citriformis*.

more susceptible to benomyl at 10 and 100 ppm concentrations.

Such simple laboratory assays can be used to evaluate selective effects of

pesticides on insect fungi. Use of inhibiting compounds (such as benomyl) should be avoided during insect fungus epizootics. □

A simplified method for sampling leaffolders (LFs) and planthoppers

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We developed a sequential sampling plan and designed a simple pegboard for recording LF, planthopper (brown planthopper [BPH] and whitebacked planthopper [WBPH]), and predator field populations. The goal was a simplified procedure that farmers can use in making IPM decisions.

Sampling models were based on distribution patterns and thresholds generated on the IRRI farm; in Mabitac and Liliw towns, Laguna; and in several fields in Batangas, Philippines.

LF distribution fitted the negative binomial distribution with a clumping coefficient (K) of 1.1. Thresholds were 1-2 larvae/hill, assuming a 20% chance of making an incorrect pest control decision.

Sequential sampling for BPH and WBPH was based on a binomial distribution model. It was developed from a regression curve drawn by correlating percentage of hills infested

1. A pegboard to record incidence of rice insect pests for making decisions on whether insecticide treatment is needed for LF, BPH, and WHPH. IRRI, 1988.

with 10 or more planthoppers and average number of hoppers per hill. This relationship allows samples to be classified into "presence" or "absence" of pest. A hill with fewer than 10 planthoppers is classified as 0; one with 10 or more is classified as 1.

Predators (predatory spiders, beetles, and crickets) were included in the model by counting major predators on the first five hills.

We tested the model with 66 samples from the IRRI farm and 166 samples from other Philippine sites.

Hills and numbers of insects on a hill are tallied by moving matchsticks or pegs across a series of holes in the pegboard (Fig. 1). The board is divided

into three decisionmaking fields: do not treat, continue counting, treat. Pictures of the pest species and their predators and the insect names are provided for comparison.

We used the board to record intensive sampling (20 hills/field) for LF in Mabitac (16 sampling occasions) and in Liliw (17 sampling occasions). Intensive and sequential sampling agreed 90% of the time (Fig. 2). In general, sequential sampling reduced the number of samples required for a decision on insecticide treatment by about 60% for LF and by about 70% for planthoppers. The board is being tested with farmers. □

2. Average number of samples required with intensive and sequential sampling to reach decisions on whether to control LF and BPH.

Effect of neem seed bitters (NSB) and neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) on pests of mungbean following rice

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Mungbean *Vigna radiata* is commonly grown Jan-Apr in the rice - mungbean cropping pattern in the Philippines. We evaluated the efficacy of NSB at 5,000 ppm, NSKE 3%, and monocrotophos at 0.3 kg ai/ha at 2 sites Jan-Mar 1988 to control insect pests. Plot size was 40 m².

Mungbean variety Pag-asa 5 was sprayed 3 times at Imbunia, Jaen, Nueva Ecija, and 4 times at Baloc, Santo Domingo, Nueva Ecija, at 15-d intervals beginning 20 d after sowing. A controlled-droplet applicator was used to apply NSB; NSKE, insecticide, or water (control) was applied with a high-volume knapsack sprayer. Damage by leaffolders (LFs) (*Sylepta* sp. and *Lamprosema* sp.) was recorded to the pod-forming stage; percent damage from pod borers *Etiella* sp., *Maruca* sp.,